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Transforming Laser-Scanned 750 kW Turbine Surface Geometry Data into Smooth CAD for CFD Simulations

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Abstract. This paper presents a method for automatically reconstructing and smoothing surfaces from laser-scanned wind turbine blades. The aim is to accurately reconstruct turbine blade surfaces in the absence of an accurate CAD model. The input consists of a series of imperfectly aligned blade point clouds, and the output is a CFD surface mesh. The automatic process starts by segmenting the blade into as many sections as there are points in the spanwise direction of the target CFD mesh. Each segment is prepared for conversion into a periodic B-spline by undergoing angular sorting, application of the Iterative Closest Point algorithm, and light smoothing with the Savitzky-Golay filter. The final surface mesh consists of a series of B-spline airfoils with matching control points fitted on a series of spanwise nonperiodic splines. The smoothed airfoils closely match the noisy point cloud data across the entire blade. Three blades of a single turbine were scanned and meshed. The maximum distance between the blade tips of the three clouds is 2.5 cm (0.1% radius). Minor differences in airfoil profiles were observed, but they had negligible effects on lift and drag. Pitch torques were slightly more affected.

1. Introduction

The WINSENT test site shown to the right is located on a plateau behind a forested escarpment at the onset of the Swabian Alps at GK3 coordinates 3561676, 5392228. The site features four 100 m meteorological masts and two 750 kW wind turbines with a 72 m hub height and 50 m rotor diameter. Its planing and installation results from a significant amount of over over many years through projects such as LIDARcomplex, KonTest and WINSENT [1, 2]. It now provides real-world aerodynamic and meteorological data such as live transient loads, deformations, and power. It has sensors that measure the ground temperature and detect the presence of birds; ultrasonic anemometers, a barometer, turbulence and climate instruments, webcams, and adjustable mobile lidars. It will serve current and future projects such as WINSENTvalid, MERIDIONAL, and TopoPro to address research questions concerning the impact of complex terrain such as hills and forests on the local wind field and on the wind turbine loads and performance while also providing a basis for experimental and numerical method

Figure 1: WINSENT test site.

development and validation. Within the WINSENTvalid project, other research institutions will also fly drones and gliders to intensively observe the local wind field under varied weather conditions and to study specific meteorological phenomena different atmospheric boundary layer stratifications.

Given the test site's importance for multiple research groups today and in the future, it was necessary to obtain the most accurate geometric representation of the installed wind turbine blades, to enable accurate finite element shell structures and URANS or DDES CFD simulations. The primary focus of this study was the meticulous reconstruction of wind turbine blade surface geometries. The key objectives were to capture blade geometries as cross-sections at various spanwise positions and to minimize errors arising from the scanning process, alignment discrepancies, and inconsistent point positions across the blade span. In addition, although the blades are in good condition and no signs of erosion have been observed visually or in the scans, they were recovered from a decommissioned wind farm and are approximately 20 years old. Possible ensuing blade-specific wear and the difficulty to retrieve precise information on the original design thus further reinforced the decision to scan each blade individually. Besides, the scan data and derived geometries can be freely distributed ¹.

1.1. Prior Art

Previous collaborations [3] emphasized the importance of scanning and postprocessing turbine blades, showing how even small geometric differences between actual and designed blade shapes significantly impact aerodynamics. Other research [4] details reconstructing wind turbine blade geometry from sectioned 3D point clouds by identifying matching airfoils from a database and highlights the challenges in realigning the point clouds to form a single geometry. In another study [5], a methodology for reconstructing airfoil profiles from noisy 3D scan data was introduced. The process included thinning the data points using a recursive weighted local least-squares method (RWLLS), ordering them by creating a profile polygon and modifying nodes, and then reconstructing a smooth profile with B-spline curves, thus mitigating noise and outlier points. Another publication [6] described a method for redesigning wind turbine blades using reverse engineering and computer-aided design (CAD). The process involved setting up a measurement coordinate system, segmenting the blade for scanning, and aligning the point cloud data. Yet another work [7] used 3D-scanning for model aircraft geometry reconstruction, developing an open-source C++ library that, despite its innovation, diverges too significantly from this study for code reuse. Finally, [8] found that erosion-induced irregularities of up to 0.8% chord size at the leading edge may reduce the annual energy production by 3%.

As for the approach presented in this paper, it differs from the state of the art in that it automatically generates an accurate, high-resolution, 2D and 3D smooth and complete blade surface directly from the pressure side, suction side, leading edge and trailing edge point clouds without using standard airfoil data. It provides a CFD-ready surface mesh without user interaction.

2. Methodology

2.1. Scanning Procedure

Shortly before assembly, the three blades of the southern wind turbine were scanned with a Leica ScanStation P20 pulsed laser scanner by the Institute for Photogrammetry and Geoinformatics of the University of Stuttgart (ifp). They were placed on support structures (figure 2, left) close to the ground on the test field, which allowed scanning of both the pressure and suction sides (PS and SS). The blades were then mounted on the hub, which was still on the ground (figure 2,

¹ The scan data, the generated airfoils, and the resulting geometry of the blades with both open and closed trailing edges are available on a dataverse: <https://doi.org/10.18419/darus-3859>

right). This arrangement allowed them to be rotated along their radial axis, which facilitated the successive scanning of their leading and trailing edges (LE and TE). The goal was to overlap the edges with the PS and SS, to keep the angle between laser and surface normal below 60° as shown in figure 2 (center), and to allow margin for the increase in angle due to the spanwise displacement of the laser. The threshold value of 60° was set after a test campaign showed that angles beyond this point resulted in cloud surface roughness exceeding our accuracy target, due to larger laser projection areas on the blade, which reduce accuracy and point density. The distance between the points scanned from the surface was maintained between 4 mm and 8 mm. The blade tips were also specifically scanned with the laser scanner positioned perpendicular to them. However, the scanning process faced challenges. Due to the blade's length and space

Figure 2: Scanning the blades. (a) PS and SS arrangement. (b) Zones of accuracy for LE and TE (schematic). (c) LE and TE arrangement.

constraints, more scans per side were required to limit scanning angles and ensure a dense enough distribution of scanned points. Additionally, while the support structures were essential, they obscured parts of the blades, necessitating movement of the blades between scans. As a result, the PS and SS were scanned 2 or 3 times each, leading to a total of 24 point clouds, with a point density of approximately one point every 4 mm. It's worth noting that the LE and TE scans showed deformations due to the blade's own weight, ranging between 10 and 20 cm at the tip.

2.2. Postprocessing of the Point Clouds

The reconstruction of a surface mesh for CFD is achieved by following a process that can be divided into three steps, each of which will be thoroughly described in this section. These steps are ① manual preparation of the 3D point clouds; ② automatic conversion to airfoils; and ③ final smoothing and postprocessing. The last two steps could be executed together, but they were separated to allow easier and faster tuning of the smoothing parameters. Additionally, they are executed in an iterative manner. As such, ② generates a set of trailing edges smoothed along the span, which are further smoothed by ③ and then reused as input by ②. This iterative approach reduces errors in cloud alignment and trailing edge positioning by enforcing a proper point distribution.

2.2.1. Postprocessing Step ① – Manual Preparation of the 3D Point Clouds

Before transforming the point clouds from the laser scanner into a CAD model suitable for aerodynamic analyses, several preprocessing steps were required. First, the blades in the point clouds were isolated from their environment and then manually cleaned to remove any obvious unwanted features such as support structures, smearing due to the laser beam's high angle of incidence relative to the blade's surface normal, and the numbering paint at the tip. Then, the partial scans per side were merged, as shown in figure 3, where 3 point clouds are gradually merged along the span of the SS of the blade. The colors represent the distance from the middle cloud. Aligning the different point clouds taken from one blade was necessary due to the scanner not being positioned at the same location, resulting in different reference coordinates. Various methods were tested to calculate the rigid transformation matrices that align the clouds, but

Table 1: Input point clouds resulting from step ① .

Suction side	SS of lead- ing edge	PS of lead- ing edge	Pressure side	SS of trail- ing edge	PS of trail- ing edge
SS	LE-SS	LE-PS	PS	TE-SS	TE-PS

the best result was obtained by manually tuning the final position of the PS, SS, LE, and TE segments. This is because considering the blade’s length of 25 m, a very small alignment angle error at the root can lead to significant differences at the tip. For instance, 1 degree at the root translates to a 44 cm offset at the tip. Temporary sticker targets, attached to the blades during the scanning process, served as reference points to aid alignment, as shown in figure 4. These reference points, combined with the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) surface matching algorithm on overlapping portions of the clouds, facilitated their alignment. After alignment, the TE and LE point clouds were unbent using a 200-element piecewise linear beam bending model computed with the symbeam Python package. No material properties were available, so the estimated weight distribution and second moment of area were derived from the chord and thickness distribution along the blade span. Taking advantage of linearity, it was thus possible to remove any bending by iteratively removing the bending curve from the LE and TE clouds until they were perfectly aligned with the SS and PS clouds, which were themselves not bent. The total unbending is blade and side dependent and amounts to about 10 cm at the blade tip. The impact on the shape of the 2D airfoil section is negligible, but the step was necessary to start the automatic 2D alignment procedure with minimal distances between the point clouds. The leading and trailing edge clouds are also manually divided into two clouds each, at the approximate position of the edge. This division allows for better angular sorting of their points, which is an essential step in the savgol filtering and spline generation of step ② . The edge cloud division also enables generating a more accurate alignment matrix for both parts by appropriately using either the PS or the SS LE side with the ICP algorithm. The outcome of

Figure 3: Merging of three point clouds to form the PS of one blade. Colored by distance from the middle cloud.

this manual preprocessing step is the creation of a file representing the surface of the blade using two preprocessed sets of the six 3D clouds listed in table 1. One set is for the body of the blade and the other is for the tip, which is treated differently by skipping any automatic filtering and alignment.

2.2.2. Postprocessing Step ② – Automatic Reconstruction of the Airfoils

A Python program was developed to manage and process the 3D point clouds, sorting the blade and its spanwise segments into custom classes and also using the CloudComPy API to the CloudCompare software. First, the program extracts a series of airfoils from those clouds as segments having 8 mm to 12 mm thickness in the spanwise direction. The PS and SS clouds are filtered by removing points whose normal direction deviates significantly from that of the scanner. Next, each point is locally scaled based on the chord length at its z-value (radius), enabling the flattening of points from varying spanwise positions with minimal noise in the point distribution. At this point, the four clouds segments are automatically and progressively aligned to the SS cloud using the ICP algorithm. The process is as such: align LE-SS onto SS and then reuse the resulting transformation matrix for LE-PS; then similarly align TE-SS and reuse

for TE-PS; and to conclude align PS on the combination of LE-PS and TE-PS. The best results were obtained when calculating the ICP transformation matrix using only the regions of overlap of the bounding boxes of source and target(s) clouds and by taking a slightly larger spanwise segment from the computation of that matrix. Optimal results were obtained by calculating the ICP transformation matrix using cloud segments that were slightly larger in spanwise direction than the actual segments to be aligned, and by considering only the overlapping regions of the source and target.

The program creates a curve for each cloud slice using a savgol-filter [9], then optionally, to increase stability, iteratively realigns the scanned blade segments on it. For consistency in subsequent 3D alignments, 2D splines are created by a least-squares fit with smoothing, using a constant knot distribution in parametric space. The control points from these 2D splines are then further adapted by undergoing 3D smoothing and being distributed on another spline in the spanwise direction. To determine leading and trailing blade edges, curvature peaks are identified. These peaks undergo spanwise smoothing and then serve as input for subsequent iterations of the cloud slicing and smoothing algorithm.

The coverage of the trailing edge scan is in some parts incomplete, because it is sharp and at some places slightly cambered, thus partially hiding the pressure side from the scanner. This makes alignment between the trailing edge and the pressure side scans more difficult and thus the TE scan is processed to increase point density. As such, it is first split to focus on its pressure side and then lightly filtered before laying a non-periodic spline to then insert interpolated points in the shadowed area.

Next, there is a progressive alignment of the four different segments. Then, portions of the leading and trailing edges are filtered out based on their y-value, which corresponds to the distance from the quarter chord line roughly along the chord itself, to avoid masking the PS and SS clouds with the lower quality (high angle) portions of the TE and LE clouds. Then the indices of each of these point cloud segments are sorted to allow subsequently generating a periodic spline for each airfoil. This is achieved by assuming an approximate scanner position and calculating the angle at which the scanner beams each point along the airfoil. Before a spline is generated for each airfoil, a savgol filtered loop of points (the draft airfoil), is generated. Then, in a user-defined number of iterations the four segments are iteratively aligned. An overview of

Figure 4: Merged point clouds colored by reflection intensity and their 108 airfoils in white.

this airfoil reconstruction procedure is shown in the flow chart of figure 5.

2.2.3. Postprocessing Step ③ – Final Smoothing and Postprocessing

The generated splines are redistributed to start precisely at the trailing edge, taking the smoothed edge positions saved from the previous run of the program. The splines of the individual airfoils are then modified to eliminate curvature when reaching the trailing edge. The decision to apply a no-curvature condition at the trailing edge was made due to irregularities in the scan data caused by the thinness of the edge and the challenging transition between scans, ensuring consistency with observed and scanned airfoil sections. This involves moving the last control points on the pressure and suction sides of the airfoil to align them with the extended line shown in figure 6 (a), where the dots represent the control points of the spline. A bisector line, also shown, is drawn between the pressure and suction extended lines, and the trailing edge control point is adjusted to lie on this bisector at the position where the airfoil's thickness,

Figure 5: Flowchart for step ②, the automatic reconstruction of the airfoils.

computed from the point cloud, reaches a user-defined minimum. For the currently analyzed blades, this minimum TE thickness was set to 1.2% of the local blade chord, which agrees to visual inspection. The influence of this thickness on the bisector line should be minimal, while that on the extension lines more important; however, the goal of this limiter is rather to ensure that no unphysically thin TE will cause irregularities in the mesh. The last three control points on both sides of the blade are aligned and then smoothed in three dimensions. In the process of doing the final 3D smoothing, the three control points of the spline that define the trailing edge are treated separately to ensure that the trailing edge thickness, angle, and position evolve smoothly along the span. These given values are thus splined, resulting in the airfoils shown in figure 6 (b). Having identified the bisector line point, the method generates a second series

(a) TE Adjustment procedure.

(b) TE processing during 3D smoothing.

Figure 6: Adjustments of the airfoils at the trailing edge.

of airfoils with open trailing edges. The use of such trailing edges aligns with common CFD practices in the wind energy industry and scientific research, where a flat trailing edge is preferred over a sharp or rounded one. The process utilizes a non-periodic spline, originating from the original airfoil. This spline incorporates the same knots along its length, excluding the trailing edge to avoid curvature. The last three knots are strategically placed on top of each other to prevent curvature, and three additional control points are set in a straight line, ensuring a flat end to the airfoil. This intermediate step precedes the final three-dimensional smoothing. For this final smoothing, allowing for automatic placement of knots in the parametric space along the blade's radius has proven more effective than manual placement, adapting effectively to the blade's complexity. There, the B-spline method is also more effective than the Akima spline or the Savitzky-Golay filter, as it yielded airfoils that are smooth and yet close to the original set of 2D segment splines. An overview of this final smoothing and postprocessing procedure is shown

in the flow chart of figure 7. Finally, the robustness of the Python program used in steps ②

Figure 7: Flowchart for step ③, the final smoothing and postprocessing procedure.

and ③ enabled the processing of the three turbine blades without needing to adjust parameters specifically for each blade, despite their small geometrical differences and significant variations in point cloud density. Various iterative procedures will work, but for the most detailed results presented in this paper of the 193-segment blade the process was run as follows: Run ② once without and twice with reuse of the computed LE and TE positions; then run ③ once and then run ② and ③ four times in a row, and at one point reducing the 3D smoothing and turning off the iterative realignment of the blade segments on the Savgol-filtered curve.

3. Results and Discussion

Two different discretization levels were explored: 108 and 193 airfoils along the span. The former is generally considered sufficient for URANS simulations, while the latter is the standard level used for wind turbine simulations at the institute, ensuring proper refinement near the blade root and the ability to run DDES simulations. The impact on the resulting blade geometry is minimal, especially considering that the industry standard practice is to define the CAD of a blade using between 10 and 30 stations along the span and to interpolate between them using a software-dependent interpolation strategy.

For the 108 airfoil test, figure 8 shows segment 32, which was automatically generated by the program. The differences between the subsampled cloud (which was slightly filtered to minimize spanwise discrepancies) and the 3D smoothed airfoil are shown, along with the inviscid pressure coefficient distribution on the airfoil, calculated with XFOIL. The non-viscous XFOIL was used to avoid viscous smoothing and to clearly show the surface-induced pressure jumps. As such, the performance of the smoothing method was evaluated by observing the suction peak at different angles of attack (AoA) and the agreement between the original and smoothed airfoil pressure distributions. To avoid focusing on the trailing edge adjustments, the last 3% of the blade is left out of this figure.

For the 193 segment blade, the 2D B-spline of segment 110 prior to 3D smoothing as generated from the point clouds is shown in figure 9 (a) along with the clouds in their pre-alignment position and prior to savgol filtering. The blade-to-blade differences for that segment are shown in figure 9 (b) and for chord and twist in figure 10. The magnitudes of the geometric differences shown in figure 9 (b) are representative of the differences found at other spanwise positions. There and for the calculation of the polars, the three airfoils were scaled and derotated using a consistent factor, ensuring the preservation of their pitch axes, as indicated by the cross

Figure 8: Blade A segment 32 of 108, at 37% radius. Left: Subsampled and 3D-smoothed airfoils. Right: Pressure distribution on subsampled and 3D-smoothed airfoils calculated with nonviscous XFOIL at different AoAs.

(a) The original four cloud segments of blade A after step ① and the resulting 2D spline. (b) The final 3D splines of the three blades, as used in the polar calculation.

Figure 9: Geometrical inspection of segment 110 located at 79% rotor radius.

Figure 10: The resulting chord and twist distributions along the span of the blades.

in the figure. The impact of smoothing and blade variations on CFD was evaluated using FLOWer [10] exclusively in unsteady mode for the polars in figure 11. FLOWer, developed at DLR (German Aerospace Center) and refined at IAG, solves compressible Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations for rotorcraft and wind energy simulations. The polars were obtained by running FLOWer at 63 equidistant angles of attack from -12° to 19° for each blade at the same relative blade radius of segment 110/193, no stall angles of attack were considered because our 2D URANS method is not adequate for this. Convergence was accelerated using a dual time-stepping Runge-Kutta scheme and a three-step multigrid method. Spatial discretization used a second-order central difference Jameson-Schmidt-Turkel (JST) scheme. The solver was configured to match typical operating conditions of this wind turbine at the currently considered blade segment, so a Reynolds number of 4.2 million and an inflow velocity corresponding to a Mach number of 0.2 were used. Each physical timestep was solved with 25 inner iterations, and a total of 500 steps were taken, taking 100 timesteps per convective time. The mesh consisted of a structured boundary layer extrusion ending after a distance of 150 chord lengths using 96 layers by 172 airfoil cells forming a flat trailing edge. A $y^+ < 0.5$ condition was maintained over the entire airfoil, and the structured airfoil mesh complied with the standard meshing approach as well as the far-field and no-slip wall boundary conditions commonly used at IAG for such computations.

Small differences between the geometries and pressure distributions of the scanned and

Figure 11: URANS-generated polars of segment 110 for the three turbine blades.

smoothed profiles were observed for all segments, similar to those shown for segments 32/108 and 110/193. The excellent agreement of the pressure distributions on the wing demonstrates the preservation of the cloud geometry. Except at the root and tip, the observed differences between the chord lengths of the three blades were within the $\pm 1\%$ standard tolerances (IEC 61400-22) mentioned by [11]. The latter also observed 2% to 4% differences in the lift coefficient, while the polars calculated for this study showed lift differences of 0.1. The moment coefficients remain small, as desired, with blade-to-blade differences reaching 0.02. To note is that the results are influenced by the local chord and twist of the airfoils on each blade: segment 110's chord and twist differ between the blades and the polars were calculated to maintain these differences. As such, variations due to both airfoil shape and 3D characteristics of the blade were captured.

Accuracy in point cloud data reflects the true, often irregular shapes of scanned objects, but smoothing to reduce noise can compromise this accuracy, slightly altering the physical shape representation. It's thus crucial to balance point cloud processing with the object's geometry fidelity versus CAD model representations. Additionally, the URANS/DDES meshing method's resolution, with a maximal cell edge length of about 10 cm, means minor surface discrepancies might not fully translate into the final surface model. The twist distribution revealed irregularities at the root and tip for two blades, attributed to minimal smoothing to preserve accuracy and higher spline fitting weights for root and tip to reflect end cross-section sizes accurately. Moreover, accurately identifying leading and trailing edges is challenging at these rounded sections due to the difficulty in pinpointing maximum curvature points.

Blade expansion or contraction due to temperature changes is minimal, given glass fiber's low thermal expansion coefficient ($0.03 \text{ mm m}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$). Yet, wind turbines can experience significant in-plane and out-of-plane deformations and torsion, leading to airfoil shape alterations along the blade, such as bulges, which affect aerodynamics [12, 13].

4. Conclusion

This paper demonstrated an innovative method for interpolating and smoothing wind turbine blade surfaces from laser-scanned data. The process is largely automated and it starts from point clouds to culminate in a precise CFD-ready surface mesh. Using this new method, this study captured and quantified aerodynamic deviations between the blades of a turbine using URANS CFD models, showing that the interpolation and smoothing process closely matches the point cloud data, with minimal aerodynamic impact from blade variations within standard tolerances. Nonetheless, local aeroacoustic effects and 3D flow effects along the blade span could be more significant.

For future studies, laser scanning could be accelerated by slightly reducing the point cloud density for the PS and SS. Efforts should also be made to reduce the number of scans, ideally

to one per blade, effectively eliminating the need for point cloud alignment. A careful iterative positioning of the TE is critical to generating consistent airfoil profiles from the scan data. Finally, it would be interesting to evaluate the impact of the various algorithm parameters on the accuracy of the surface and its smoothness and aerodynamic response. Future research will use the detailed blade geometry to validate 3D blade and full turbine URANS and DDES models, including fluid-structure interaction and validation against field measurements, to improve turbine performance predictions and explore adaptations such as flap integration and pitch adjustments. This high-precision geometry is thus essential for wind turbine research.

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References

- [1] Guma G, Bucher P, Letzgus P, Lutz T and Wüchner R 2022 *Wind Energy Science* **7** 1421–1439
- [2] Letzgus P, Guma G and Lutz T 2022 *Wind Energy Science* **7** 1551–1573
- [3] Schepers J, Boorsma K, Gomez-Iradi S, Shen W, Schreck S, Sorensen N, Madsen H and Schulz C 2014 The latest results on experimental wind turbine aerodynamics *Proceedings of the IEA Annex 29 Mexnext Conference* (The Netherlands: ECN)
- [4] Bermek M and Gentry R 2021 Reconstruction of wind turbine blade geometry and shape matching of airfoil profiles to point clouds *29th International Workshop on Intelligent Computing in Engineering (EG-ICE)* (USA: Georgia Institute of Technology)
- [5] Ghorbani H and Khameneifar F 2021 *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering* **8** 740–755
- [6] Sun W, Tao Q, Kang J and Zhuang X 2013 Establishing large-scale wind turbine blade cad model based on reverse engineering *19th International Conference on Automation & Computing* (Brunel University, London, UK: IEEE)
- [7] van Brügge L, Çetin K M, Koeberle S J, Thiele M, Sturm F and Hornung M 2023 *CEAS Aeronautical Journal* **14** 455–467
- [8] Vimalakanthan K, van der Mijle Meijer H, Bakhmet I and Schepers G 2023 *Wind Energy Science* **8** 41–69
- [9] Savitzky A and Golay M J E 1964 *Analytical Chemistry* **36** 1627–1639
- [10] Raddatz J and Fassbender J K 2005 Block structured navier-stokes solver flower *MEGAFLOW - Numerical Flow Simulation for Aircraft Design* ed Kroll N and Fassbender J K (Springer Berlin Heidelberg) pp 27–44
- [11] Gonzaga P, Toft H, Worden K, Dervilis N, Bernhammer L, Stevanovic N and Gonzales A 2022 *Wind Energy* **25** 1060–1076
- [12] Lehnhoff S, Gómez González A and Seume J R 2020 *Wind Energy Science* **5** 1411–1423
- [13] Schulz V, Stoffel R and Zorn H 2018 Structural optimization of 3d wings under aerodynamic loads: Topology and shell *Notes on Numerical Fluid Mechanics and Multidisciplinary Design* vol 138 (Springer)